

DEADLINE EXTENSION – OA Diamond Survey

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Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

The deadline for the OA Diamond & Institutional Publishing Landscape Survey has been extended. You now have until 10/05/23 to complete the survey.

To provide appropriate resources we need to hear from more IPSPs. Shape the future of Diamond Open Access and provide your feedback before May 10th.

We are here to support you with the survey. If you encounter technical issues while filling in the survey please contact the project team at surveysupport@diamasproject.eu. For general questions, visit our [contact page](#).

In addition, we still have SURVEY-A-THONS planned to support respondents, with further sessions being developed.

Funded by
the European Union